

Oxalatoberyllates

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Methods for the preparation of several oxalatoberyllates of organic base cations, viz., pyridinium, quinolinium, β - and γ -picolinium, guanidinium, and of hexammine cobalt (III) ion are presented. A simple method for the preparation of pure beryllium oxalate is given. The infrared spectra and results of TGA studies of the oxalatoberyllates are presented and discussed.

BERYLLIUM oxalate, in aqueous solution shows peculiar molar conductance properties which is attributed to the presence¹ of highly dissociated dichelate $\text{Be}[\text{Be}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$. The existence of the anion $\text{Be}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2^{2-}$ ($\log \beta_{12} = 5.7$)² is established by the isolation³ of double oxalates of the type $\text{M}_2^{12}\text{Be}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$ where M^+ is an alkali metal or ammonium ion and also by the extraction of beryllium by long chain amines⁴. The present authors isolated several oxalatoberyllates of organic base cations and of hexammine cobalt(III) ion. The preparation of these compounds and study of their properties are presented in this paper.

The preparation of pure beryllium oxalate, the starting material for the isolation of these oxalatoberyllates, is however a complicated one. In the usual procedures it is prepared by reacting beryllium hydroxide with oxalic acid. If the beryllium hydroxide added remain in excess to that required by oxalic acid, basic beryllium oxalates result and the product is very difficult to crystallise; again if the amount of oxalic acid becomes in excess, the excess oxalic acid is difficult to separate even by repeated recrystallisation.

A simple method for preparing pure beryllium oxalate, $\text{BeC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, is also presented here.

Experimental

Quinoline was distilled before use. Hexamminecobalt(III) oxohexacarbonatoberyllate used for the preparation of hexamminecobalt(III) oxalatoberyllate was prepared according to Sengupta⁵. Beryllium oxalate used for the work, was prepared according to the following equation

For the purpose, calculated amount of basic beryllium acetate was dissolved by boiling in an oxalic acid

solution, and acetic acid was removed by boiling the mixture repeatedly and beryllium oxalate was crystallised by evaporation.

General methods of preparation of $(\text{BH})_2\text{Be}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$, where B = pyridine, quinoline, β and γ -picoline and guanidine—The compounds were obtained by adding stoichiometric quantities of beryllium oxalate dissolved in water to a solution of the organic base containing the calculated amount of oxalic acid. The resulting mixture was then evaporated and allowed to crystallise on water bath. The first crop of crystals (second crop in the case of guanidinium oxalatoberyllate) was separated by suction, washed with ice-cold water, pressed between folds of filter paper and finally dried.

Preparation of hexamminecobalt(III) oxalatoberyllate $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{Be}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Hexamminecobalt(III) oxohexacarbonatotetra-beryllate, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{Be}_4\text{O}(\text{CO}_3)_6] \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 g), was dissolved in a solution (15 ml) of oxalic acid (1.3 g) and placed over water bath. Crystals, which appeared immediately, were removed and the filtrate was allowed to crystallise. The crystals (which appeared on concentration) were removed by suction, washed with ice-cold water, pressed between folds of filter paper and dried in air.

The analytical results of the compounds are given in Table 1.

The TGA data (Fig. 1) were recorded in a manually operated thermobalance by heating the compounds (Pyridinium and quinolinium oxalatoberyllate) at the increasing rate of 2° per minute.

The infrared spectra of the complexes (Table 2) were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer apparatus in KBr pellet in the region of 400–4000 cm^{-1} (Pyridinium and quinolinium oxalatoberyllates) and 700–4000 cm^{-1} in all other cases.

TABLE-1. ANALYSIS OF OXALATOBERYLLATES

Sl. No.	Complex	Found %					Calculated %				
		C	H	N	Be	Oxalate	C	H	N	Be	Oxalate
1.	(C ₅ H ₅ NH) ₂ Be(C ₂ O ₄) ₂	48.78	3.54	8.09	2.79	51.24	48.68	3.51	8.12	2.61	51.01
2.	(C ₉ H ₇ NH) ₂ Be(C ₂ O ₄) ₂	59.19	3.51	6.35	2.08	39.77	59.32	3.63	6.29	2.02	39.85
3.	β-(CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ NH ₂)Be(C ₂ O ₄) ₂			7.43	2.45	47.40			7.51	2.42	47.19
4.	γ-(CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ NH ₂)Be(C ₂ O ₄) ₂			7.50	2.38	47.36			7.51	2.42	47.19
5.	[(NH ₃) ₂ C : NH.H] ₂ Be(C ₂ O ₄) ₂ .3H ₂ O			26.54	2.69	54.07			26.31	2.79	54.49
6.	[Co(NH ₃) ₆] ₂ [Be(C ₂ O ₄) ₃].3H ₂ O			18.47	2.70	57.01			18.05	2.90	56.71

CURVE I. [C₅H₅NH]₂Be[C₂O₄]₂
 CURVE II. [C₉H₇NH]₂Be[C₂O₄]₂

Fig. 1

TABLE 2 -INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS (ν IN CM⁻¹) OF OXALATO-BERYLLATES

I. (C ₅ H ₅ NH) ₂ Be(C ₂ O ₄) ₂ :	3080-2987(B), 1680(VS), 1475(VS), 1400(VS), 1270(VS), 1190(S), 1048(S), 920(VS), 870(M), 815(VS), 750(VS).
II. (C ₉ H ₇ NH) ₂ Be(C ₂ O ₄) ₂ :	3400-3300(WB), 2650-2550(WS), 1720(VS), 1620-1550(T), 1400(VS), 1295(VW), 1270(S), 1265(S), 924(S), 850(M), 820(S), 760(W).
III. β-(CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ NH) ₂ Be(C ₂ O ₄) ₂ :	3333(W), 1724(VS), 1538(M), 1471(VW), 1389(VS), 1266(VS), 939(VS), 862(M), 833(S), 790(W).
IV. γ-(CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ NH) ₂ Be(C ₂ O ₄) ₂ :	3330(W), 1724(VS), 1639(W), 1493(W), 1389(VS), 1266(S), 930(S), 862(M), 833(S), 790(W).
V. [Co(NH ₃) ₆] ₂ [Be(C ₂ O ₄) ₃].3H ₂ O :	3226(S), 1724(VS), 1650-1613(WB), 1389(VS), 1325(M), 1266(S), 926(S), 862(M), 830(S).

V = very; M = medium; W = weak; S = strong; B = broad; D = doublet; T = triplet.

Results and Discussion

The compounds of the organic base cations (BH)₂ Be(C₂O₄)₂, are all colourless, crystalline solids. [Co(NH₃)₆]₂[Be(C₂O₄)₃.3H₂O is yellow in colour. The compounds are soluble in water but are insoluble in common organic solvents. Pyridinium, quinolinium and picolinium salts (β- and γ-) are insoluble in pyridine, quinoline and β- and γ-picolines respectively. From the TGA data (Fig. 1) it is observed that the decomposition of the pyridinium salt results in the formation of an unstable intermediate at 255° and is complete at around 400°. In the case of quinolinium salt the formation of an unstable intermediate is observed at 210° and the decomposition is complete at about 300°. In both the cases from the percent loss in weight (vide below) the unstable intermediate compounds appear to be anhydrous beryllium oxalate, BeC₂O₄, and the final decomposition products are found to be beryllium oxide.

A number of assignments involving different symmetries have been given for the oxalate ion in the solid state, both D_{2h} and D₂ arrangements have been found^{6,7}. The spectra of oxalate ion in complexes of the type K₂M^{II}(C₂O₄)₂ has been assigned on the basis of C_{2v} symmetry by Fujita et al⁸ and concluded that the spectra of all the oxalate complexes are essentially similar regardless of the kind of the metal and the combining ratio of the metal to ligand. A certain degree of covalently bound oxalate group

however shows a very strong absorption⁹ in the neighbourhood of 1700 cm^{-1} whereas ionically bound oxalates show a band in the region $1600\text{--}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The oxalatoberyllates of organic base or hexaamminecobalt(III) cation showed strong absorption bands near 1724 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{as}\text{ C=O}$) and around 1400 cm^{-1} , the latter may be attributed to ν_{sym} (C-O) & ν_{C-C} . Strong band was also observed in the complexes around 820 cm^{-1} due to the Be-O coordination in the oxalatoberyllates.

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References

1. N. V. SIDGWICK, 'Chemical Elements and their Compounds', Oxford University Press, 1950, vol. 1, p. 216.
2. Y. COUTURLE and J. FAUCHERRE, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1970, 4, 1323.
3. A. ROSENHEIM and P. WOGG, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1897, 15, 292.
4. H. J. DE BRUIN, D. KAIRAITES and R. B. TEMPLE, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1962, 15, 457.
5. A. K. SENGUPTA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1823.
6. G. A. JEFFERY and G. S. PARRY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 5283.
7. R. L. GRIFFITH, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1943, 11, 499.
8. J. FUJITA, A. E. MARTELL and K. NAKAMOTO, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, 36, 324.
9. KOTRA V. KRISHNAMURTY and G. M. HARRIS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, 61, 214.